

Bubble circuits in saliva exchange waves with cells and neural system

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Abstract: Up to date, it has been known that saliva has some bubbles which their shapes and connections are approximately the same in all types of human. Now, the question arises that what is the origin and application of this system. In this research, we propose a model which considers the origin and the role of bubbles in transmission information from cells to neural systems and medium. In this model, DNA waves interact with cellular membranes and cause to their vibrations, by these vibrations, molecules of water move and some holes are appeared within the liquid around cells. These holes could be filled by enzymes, ions, gases like carbon dioxides, oxygen and other air molecules and surrounded by water molecules. This system forms a rotating bubble which ions and some electrical matters move on its boundary very fast and produce some electrical currents. These currents emit some waves which carry main information about DNA and its evolutions. These bubbles act like round coils and absorb smaller bubbles. These pairs of big-small bubbles form a neuron-like object. These objects join to each other and form neural-like circuit. This circuit could exchange waves with neural circuits within the brain and DNAs within cells. By taking and analyzing these waves, we could obtain main information about evolutions of human's body.

Keywords: Bubble, Neuron, Saliva, Circuit, Water memory

I.Introduction

Around 30 years ago, Jacques Benveniste published a paper in Nature and argued that water has the ability to store information and retain a memory of substances previously dissolved in it even after an arbitrary number of serial dilutions [1]. Up

to date, some investigators have tried to assert this idea or even use of its applications. For example, a group have assumed that waves originating from a strong pulsed electric field could transmit molecule information into water. They have tested this hypothesis experimentally on various biological systems like bacteria and plants. The results were very positive and encouraging: Both organisms reacted to an information imprint of a chosen substance [2]. Another group have obtained more wonderful result. They not only claims that bacterial/viral genetic matters could emit electromagnetic waves through the water around them but could be teleported. They have put two vessels in an inductor and apply a magnetic field to them. One vessel has included viral RNAs and water molecules and other has included only pure water. Then, they have used of PCR and other techniques and detected the signature of viral RNAs in second vessel. This means that the properties of genetic matters were transformed or teleported from one vessel to other [3-5].

Now, the question arises that if these experiments are true, could we use of water bubbles around cells to recover some information about evolutions of biological system? Many investigations have been done on the cell-bubble interactions and their applications in biology. For example, one work has investigated the interactions that occur between bubbles formed during decompression and cells in a 3D engineered tissue phantom. In this experiment, cell death was found to significantly increase ($p=0.0116$) following a bubble-forming decompression [6]. In parallel, in many other investigations, it has been shown that bubbles could damage cell structures and prevent of the growth of cells within culture or human/animal/plant body [7-11]. However, it seems that in spite these harmful effects, bubbles could play the role of information transmitter so. For example, they may act like extracellular vesicles which contain biological matters [12]. We couldn't detect these vesicles by light microscopes easily, however, bubbles could grow and be detected by any microscope. In addition, they form some circuits which exchange information with medium and inform us from events within cells. In this research, we consider this subject.

II. Saliva bubbles under a light microscope

We have taken salivary water from different persons and put them under a light microscope. It is interesting that all salivary waters have the same

bubble like shapes . In all of the, bubble molecules are connected to each other and form a circuit. In fact, first, big round bubbles are connected to small round bubbles by some cylindrical wire-like bubbles. Then, these pairs are connected to each other and form bubble circuits. In this circuit, light waves and water molecules move along some wire like bubbles and transform information from a big round bubble to small one or reverse. It seems that this circuit is exchanging waves with human cells and medium (See figure 1) . In figure 2, we show a pair of bubbles which are connected by a tube. It is clear that water or gas molecules are transmitted from a bubble to another and transmit some biological information , enzymes and genetic matters . In figure 3, we show that in addition to biological molecules, some electromagnetic waves could be exchanged between two bubbles. These waves carry main information about their initial cellular cells and could give us the best opportunity to consider evolutions of human's body. In figure 4, one could observe that two interacting bubble rotate very fast. Each bubble is formed from air molecules, water and ions and by their motions, some electrical currents are emerged. These currents emit some electromagnetic waves which could be taken by neural network, DNAs, RNAs and other biological circuits. In figure 5, boundary wall of a bubble divide into several lines which each of them form a separate round col and emit an special wave.

Fig 1: Salivary bubbles join to each other and form a complicated network.

Fig 2: Bubbles are connected by some hard and thick tubes

Fig 3: Bubbles exchange some electromagnetic waves

Fig 4: Two bubbles are rotating fast and exchange some waves

Fig 5: A closer look into walls of two interacting bubbles

III. A model for exchanging waves between bubble circuits, cells and medium

In this section, we propose a model which helps us to consider the origin and the role of bubble circuits in transforming information from cells to medium. In this model, first, DNAs vibrate and by their motions, their electrical charges move and

some DNA currents are emerged. These currents emit some electromagnetic waves. These waves interact with charges within the cellular membranes and cause their vibrations. On the other hand, some external sources like neurons and cells could send some external fields which force into membranes and cause to their vibrations. By these vibrations, molecules of water around the cellular membranes move. By these motions, some holes are emerged and some gases like carbon dioxide, oxygen and air molecules are confined within them. In addition, maybe, some enzymes and genetic matters also be located within the holes. These holes become bigger and absorb different molecules and ions. On the walls of this hole, molecules of water and ions are moving fast and produce some electrical currents. These current emit some electromagnetic waves which carry main information of evolutions of initial cellular sources (See figure 6). Some big bubbles act like round coils and absorb some smaller round coils. These pairs of big and small bubbles form a neuron-like system and information, water molecules, ions and electrical charges could be exchanged between two heads of them (See figure 7). These neuron-like objects join to each other and form bubble circuits. These circuits could exchange waves with brain, heart, salivary and other cells.

Fig 6: The process of formation bubbles

Fig 7: A pair of bubbles form a neural like system

Fig 8: Bubble circuits in connections with neural circuits, salivary cells and other biological system within the body.

Conclusion:

In this research, first, we have shown some photos of real interacting bubbles within the saliva and then propose a model for it. We have argued that DNA waves cause to the vibration of cellular membranes and motions of water molecules around them. Consequently, some holes are emerged which could be filled by air gases, ions and water molecules. These holes are surrounded by some ions and other electrical charges which move very fast and produce some currents. These currents emit some electromagnetic waves which have a direct relation with initial DNA waves. These holes join to each other and form bubble circuit. This circuit is very similar to neural circuit and with high probability exchange waves with it and also DNAs.

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